

ENTREPRENEDEU

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

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D7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

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Abstract	This document presents the first draft of the plan for communication activities, including communication tools, as well as dissemination activities and dissemination tools related to the first six months of the ENTREPRENEDU project.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ENTREPRENEDU project is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between European Union countries that have unbalanced business activities and fewer job opportunities, due to less developed entrepreneurial ecosystems.

ENTREPRENEDU aims to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for European education. The consortium seeks to improve the quality and outreach of both innovation and educational ecosystems, implementing a high replicable and scalable Venture Building Program for youth, an educational model for the European entrepreneurial ecosystems developed via a series of 3 Hackathons at national level, supporting concepts and ideas to become concrete solutions, thus enhancing cooperation between businesses and education providers. In the end, the **Venture Building Program will be validated in 3 different educational entities based in emerging-moderate innovators countries.**

The consortium gathers eight key innovation players of emerging-moderate (Bulgaria, Italy and Greece) and strong innovators (Ireland and Germany) EU countries, as well as innovation leaders (Belgium), **who will work together to share key information and enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for European education.**

The recommendations made in the booklet [Making the Most of Your H2020 Project](#) from the [European IPR Helpdesk](#) have been taken into account to **achieve the communication and dissemination goals, while respecting ENTREPRENEDU's general objective.**

ENTREPRENEDU's target audience is mainly divided into 5 groups (youth, academia, industry, investors and policy makers), who are interested in entrepreneurship, startups and innovation, but with different backgrounds, desires and pain points.

The Dissemination and Communication strategy includes the definition of the communication and dissemination plan, establishing its own media channels, and the creation of promotional materials and tools. The dissemination and communication strategy of the ENTREPRENEDU project aims at maximising its impact by connecting the support activities performed to the public and professional audiences. The project will combine digital channels, such as project website and social media channels, and traditional media to boost and increase its results outreach, during the project lifespan.

The Dissemination and Communication Monitoring Plan allow the consortium to effectively follow the action plan, identify Key Performance indicators and assess the impact of the overall strategy defined for the project. The impact evaluation takes into account scientific, economic and societal areas.

The current report identifies the crucial context of the ENTREPRENEDU project, having a clear image of the problem it is trying to solve and vision of the main project's results.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The European entrepreneurial landscape is still geographically unbalanced, and ending the innovation gap among different European countries and regions is still a major necessity. Indeed, it is in Europe's greatest interest to unlock the unrealised potential of regions that have not yet fully developed their innovation ecosystems outreach and capacity, in order to achieve true resilience and economic recovery through balanced business activity across the European Union. One of the ways to close this gap is to provide education schemes and supporting mechanisms for youth interested in entrepreneurship and business entities at the beginning of their professional journey (startups).

Starting from the previously written premises, ENTREPRENEDU is on a mission to create more connected, inclusive and efficient innovation ecosystems that enhance the competences of youth and educational systems to address important business challenges in a responsible way. Hence, the actions promoted by ENTREPRENEDU focus on reinforcing network connectivity within and between innovation ecosystems for sustainable business growth with high societal value, supporting youth and start-uppers in acquiring the necessary competences in overcoming the barriers of accessing both finance and market, thus acting as a bridge between educational and business sectors and enhancing connectedness between different European regions with different level of innovation.

Therefore, the general objective of the project ENTREPRENEDU is to create a highly replicable and scalable Venture Building Program – an educational model for both businesses and educational systems via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level. These Hackathons will focus on young professionals and their ideas, by supporting developed concepts (technology readiness level 2) to become concrete solutions (technology readiness level 5). In the end, the Venture Building Program will be validated in 3 different educational entities based in moderate innovators regions.

1.1 THEORETICAL APPROACH

To achieve the communication and dissemination goals, while respecting ENTREPRENEDU's general objective, we took inspiration from the recommendations made in the booklet [Making the Most of Your H2020 Project](#) from the [European IPR Helpdesk](#), which is represented in the table below.

By referring to the [Making the Most of Your H2020 Project](#) booklet, the **Deliverable 7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN** will focus mainly on the Communication and Dissemination recommendations represented in the table below, with a strategic goal to establish relevant communication and dissemination tools and channels, that will enable respective Consortium Partners to address relevant audience with appropriate communication and dissemination techniques and materials to promote ENTREPRENEDU's results and contribute to the scalability of the project.

TABLE 1: REFERENCE TO THE BOOKLET: MAKING THE MOST OF YOUR H2020 PROJECT

	COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
DEFINITION	<p>“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communication about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	<p>“The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	<p>“The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>
OBJECTIVE	<p>Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g., by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.</p>	<p>Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.</p>	<p>Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.</p>
FOCUS	<p>Inform about and promote the project and its results/success.</p>	<p>Describe and ensure results available for others to use - focus on results only!</p>	<p>Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use)</p>
TARGET AUDIENCE	<p>Multiple audiences beyond the project’s own community including media and the broad public.</p>	<p>Audiences that may take an interest in the potential use of the results (e.g., scientific community, industrial partner, policymakers).</p>	<p>People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.</p>

2 TARGET AUDIENCE

The first step toward developing a strong Dissemination and Communication strategy is deep understanding of the ENTREPRENEDU target audience and tailoring both dissemination and communication activities to the specific needs of each target group. Each target group has its own sphere of communication, and our aim is to address our target audience in a more meaningful way, and with more relatable, non-generalised content.

The ENTREPRENEDU stakeholders are key innovation players of emerging-moderate and strong innovator EU countries, as well as from innovation leaders countries, who need to work together to share key information and enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for education. With the goal of understanding them in a more meaningful and human-centric matter, we deployed a User Personas analysis of their profiles. This simple, yet very comprehensive visual technique presents an exercise of understanding the expectations of each target audience, which allows to address these target audiences with effective content through the appropriate communication and dissemination channels.

To do that, five fictional characters have been displayed, each of one representing needs, reasons “why”, limitations and social behavioural characteristics of a hypothesised group of our target users. We imagined these characters as a group of people interested in entrepreneurship, startups and innovation, but with different backgrounds, desires and pain points and tried to understand what ENTREPRENEDU could offer them to fulfil their needs, while cancelling their limitations.

2.1 YOUTH

Youth is the main target audience which represents young professionals (18-30 years old) – high schoolers and university students interested in entrepreneurship, as well as young startup owners or future entrepreneurs who are dreaming of becoming an owner of a unicorn company in Europe.

Fictional character: Emma (25), University student

- **Need:** Emma has an excellent business idea and a team, but is looking for an opportunity to gain knowledge, receive support and/or funds and create a scalable business.
- **Limitation:** Emma doesn't have financial and technological support nor the business experience or expertise to follow up with the industrial trends.
- **Opportunity:** With ENTREPRENEDU, Emma has an opportunity to participate in a Hackathon with her friends and gain experience, learn new skills and get the business support she always wanted. Finally, her idea might become a reality.

- **Communication tools:** Emma could find out about ENTREPRENEDU through bigger startup events, startup blogs or articles or social media, in particular Instagram or LinkedIn.

2.2 ACADEMIA

Academia represents educational systems members as end users of the ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building Program, as well as experts willing to support young professionals.

Fictional character: Alex (40), Professor

- **Need:** Alex wishes to understand European educational gaps and help enhance the current education system.
- **Limitation:** However, Alex is lacking time to start this research on its own.
- **Opportunity:** With ENTREPRENEDU, Alex has an opportunity to network with key innovation stakeholders, while helping young professionals just by using his knowledge and expertise.
- **Communication tools:** Alex could find out about ENTREPRENEDU through LinkedIn, Media, professional networks, conferences, academic events, blogs.

2.3 INDUSTRY

Industry represents Innovation service providers such as incubators and accelerators or networks of clusters.

Fictional character: Lois (35), Accelerator manager

- **Need:** Lois is looking for a possibility to connect with other innovation services providers and attract more startups.
- **Limitation:** Therefore, Lois needs an additional perspective towards business development and technological trends, with an aim to enhance the business services of the accelerator she runs.
- **Opportunity:** With ENTREPRENEDU, Lois gains the possibility to become more aware of the market needs and connect with actors interested to scale-up their businesses. Moreover, Lois could improve the concept of the accelerator's business services, the outreach, plus revenue streams.
- **Communication tools:** Lois could find out about ENTREPRENEDU through LinkedIn, professional networks, startup or tech events, F6S platform.

2.4 INVESTORS

Investors such as venture capitalists, family offices and business angels will be invited to the ENTREPRENEDU Hackathons with an aim to connect them with young professionals in the industry.

Fictional character: Sara (50), Investor

- **Need:** Sara is always looking for market and technology proven startups, but she is also interested in finding new disrupting companies – potential unicorns.
- **Limitation:** However, Sara has a problem keeping track with new trends and tech-development.
- **Opportunity:** With ENTREPRENEDU, Sara has an opportunity to connect with key innovation actors, both from industry and academic sectors and secure a long-term profit.
- **Communication tools:** Sara could find out about ENTREPRENEDU through professional networks, media, business magazines, F6S Platform or LinkedIn.

2.5 POLICY MAKERS

Policy Makers represent local, regional, national EU authorities in education which are crucial players of influence. The aim is to present the problem and ENTREPRENEDU solution, discuss recommendations for policy making, identify barriers and next steps, create visibility for the topic, its urgent matter, and opportunities it can bring for the economy, society and environment, if explored in the near future.

Fictional character: Michael (45), Governor

- **Need:** Michael Interested in empowering strong innovation system locally by following industry trends when tailoring legislative frameworks.
- **Limitation:** However, Michael is unaware of best practices and has difficulties in defining the path of innovation of disrupting industries, he needs insiders' information.
- **Opportunity:** With ENTREPRENEDU, Michael has an opportunity to connect with key innovation actors, both from industry and academic sectors.
- **Communication tools:** Michael could find out about ENTREPRENEDU through professional networks, pan-European events, Media or LinkedIn.

2.6 KEY MESSAGES

Key messages are an integral part of the communication and dissemination strategy as they will encourage the main stakeholders to participate in ENTREPRENEDU activities, with a focus on Hackathons. They portray relevant information project values and goals, activities, results and potential impact and they will be adapted to each target group. In table 2, we have provided examples of generic key messages for ENTREPRENEDU's specific target audience. These examples can be updated at any time accordingly taking into consideration the specific target group's needs and project's present status.

TABLE 2: LIST OF KEY MESSAGES

TARGET AUDIENCE	EXAMPLE OF A KEY MESSAGE
YOUTH	<p>Have you always dreamt of becoming a successful entrepreneur, but you don't know where to start? Join ENTREPRENEDU – a project supported by the European Union with an aim of helping young professionals to transform their ideas into concrete solutions!</p> <p>Interested in learning more about ENTREPRENEDU? Check our Instagram @entreprenedu.eu or visit our website ENTREPRENEDU.EU !</p>
ACADEMIA	<p>Looking for an opportunity to support young professionals in their dream to become entrepreneurs? Meet ENTREPRENEDU - an initiative funded under the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, with an aim to enrich entrepreneurial ecosystems for education across Europe! Join ENTREPRENEDU and enhance the impact of your expertise!</p> <p>Eager to learn more about ENTREPRENEDU? Reach us at HELLO@ENTREPRENEDU.EU or visit our website - ENTREPRENEDU.EU !</p>
INDUSTRY	<p>Are you always striving to enhance your business network? Meet ENTREPRENEDU - an initiative funded under the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, with an aim to enrich entrepreneurial ecosystems for education</p>

	<p>across Europe! With ENTREPRENEDU, you will have an opportunity to meet relevant stakeholders and bring info on latest trends impacting the European innovation ecosystem!</p> <p>Interested to learn more about this opportunity? Reach us at HELLO@ENTREPRENEDU.EU or visit our website - ENTREPRENEDU.EU !</p>
<p>INVESTORS</p>	<p>Are you looking for a new investment opportunity? Meet ENTREPRENEDU – an initiative funded under the European Commission’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, with an aim to enhance entrepreneurial ecosystems for education across Europe! ENTREPRENEDU is the source of business ideas developed by young professionals whose journey is led and supported by academic experts. Join us and discover novelties that have the potential to disrupt the industry!</p> <p>Interested in learning more? Reach us at HELLO@ENTREPRENEDU.EU or visit our website - ENTREPRENEDU.EU !</p>
<p>POLICY MAKERS</p>	<p>ENTREPRENEDU is an initiative funded under the European Commission’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, with an aim to enhance entrepreneurial ecosystems for education across Europe and connect key players of the European innovation ecosystem! Our objective is to develop a highly replicable and scalable Venture Building Program - an educational model meant for both business and educational entities which will cancel the innovation gap between diverse European countries and regions. Create a comparative of the regional innovation strategy - reach us at HELLO@ENTREPRENEDU.EU or visit our website - ENTREPRENEDU.EU and learn what is the potential impact of this Program if explored today.</p>

3 COMMUNICATION PLAN

The ENTREPRENEDU communication plan consists of proactive and well-planned communication efforts, with intriguing messaging – both in terms of type of content and in the way the content is communicated with and aim of connecting with specific key players and their engagement among innovation ecosystems, fostering networking, experience sharing and final dissemination and exploitation of ENTREPRENEDU’s most relevant outputs.

To this end, best practices of Inbound marketing will be adopted to ensure that ENTREPRENEDU communication activities reach the relevant stakeholders who will benefit from project’s final outcomes and implement them beyond. In other words, the Inbound marketing methodology will put ENTREPRENEDU’s values in front of the stakeholders at the moment when they are actually looking for what ENTREPRENEDU has to offer – a vibrant innovation network. Unlike the Outbound marketing strategy, which focuses on communication outputs only in numbers (for example: how many newsletters we have produced), Inbound measures impact as well. At the bottom line, the Inbound marketing strategy focuses mainly on them - our key stakeholders.

Inbound marketing, as it is applied to ENTREPRENEDU, involves strategic planning, content development and distribution across the most meaningful channels, implemented through the 3 main phases:

- Creation of the **Initial Awareness** about ENTREPRENEDU concepts, objectives and expected results in the European innovation ecosystem.
- Refining **Target Awareness** with up-to-date activities by informing about ENTREPRENEDU opportunities, benefits and demonstrating the first tangible and intangible results to the key stakeholders.
- Transversion to the **Strategic Implementation** which outlines maximising awareness of the key stakeholders on ENTREPRENEDU impact and demonstrating more advanced results of the project.

However, to successfully implement the purpose of the Inbound marketing methodology, it was extremely important to create a strong and easily identifiable brand identity which organically resonates with key stakeholders. Hence, in the next section of this document, we have elaborated ENTREPRENEDU brand storyline.

3.1 BRAND IDENTITY

ENTREPRENEDU brand identity is a language that communicates projects’ philosophy and values, establishes projects’ voice, and builds an emotional and professional connection with key stakeholders. Brand identity establishes a baseline tone of the ENTREPRENEDU project and becomes the springboard for the expression of the entire visual identity.

Following the idea of the young and vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem, the ENTREPRENEDU brand identity is envisioned as fun, yet professional, energetic, smart and modern. Detailed elaboration of the project’s visual identity is being developed since M1 and provided in the document named ENTREPRENEDU Brand Guidelines. The document was presented to all Consortium Partners and shared in the main project’s repository.

FIGURE 1: ENTREPRENEDU BRAND GUIDELINES

This document showcases the main branding elements, such as different versions of logotypes, colour palette, typography, and best recommendations for effective communication of the ENTREPRENEDU brand.

3.1.1 LOGOTYPES

The ENTREPRENEDU logo conceptually represents team characteristics such as collaboration, diversity and partnership, while its composition is ensuring to amplify the innovative nature

of the project. In the purpose of creating the complete visual identity of the ENTREPRENEDU project, we have developed different logo versions.

FIGURE 2: ENTREPRENEDU LOGOTYPE

FIGURE 3: ENTREPRENEDU LOGOTYPE WITH A SIGNATURE

FIGURE 4: ENTREPRENEDU LOGOTYPE - BLACK AND WHITE VERSION

FIGURE 5: ENTREPRENEDU LOGOTYPE - MONOCHROMATIC VERSIONS

3.1.2 COLOUR PALETTE

ENTREPRENEDU's visual identity has 4 primary brand colours, which are selected with an aim to enhance projects' storyline and efficiently communicated with key stakeholders:

- PANTONE RED 032C represents power.
- PANTONE DARK BLUE 273C represents professionalism.
- PANTONE BLUE 285C represents trust.
- PANTONE YELLOW 1365C represents innovation.

However, the combination of these colours exudes novelty, freshness and youth.

FIGURE 6: ENTREPRENEDU COLOUR PALETTE

3.1.3 TYPOGRAPHY

The ENTREPRENEDU projects’ communication materials adopted [Fira Sans font](#) which is available for free download at Google Fonts.

FIGURE 7: ENTREPRENEDU PRIMARY TYPOGRAPHY

Fira Sans is an inclusive font which fits Latin, Cyrillic and Greek letters. Moreover, Fira Sans font includes a wide range of accessibility options.

3.1.4 BRANDING RECOMMENDATIONS

To prevent incorrect usage of the ENTREPRENEDU logo, the Brand Guidelines include a recommendation section, which showcases the designing exclusion zone and examples of inappropriate ways of using the logo.

FIGURE 8: RECOMMENDED MINIMUM LOGO SIZE IN PRINT

FIGURE 9: EXAMPLES OF AN INAPPROPRIATE LOGO USE

3.2 CHANNELS AND TOOLS

The goal of the previously described communication plan and brand identity is to conceptualise ENTREPRENEDU values and deliver a coherent visual storyline through different assets of digital communication. With that in line and with a goal to perform a robust communication strategy, we have conveyed a set of communication efforts with an aim to increase awareness and stimulate the interest of ENTREPRENEDU key stakeholders. Therefore, in the following section, the various communication tools and channels are outlined in more detail.

3.2.1 COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

ENTREPRENEDU communication materials have been developed at the M1 and will be upgraded during the projects' lifespan by respecting suggestions made by Consortium Partners. The set of the ENTREPRENEDU official communication materials include:

- **General Word template**, created for diverse purposes of internal and external communication activities, such as writing meeting minutes, writing press releases, blog articles, simple reporting and similar.

FIGURE 10: ENTREPRENEDEDU GENERAL WORD TEMPLATE

- **Deliverable Word template**, created for the purpose of writing complex reports, strategies, and deliverables.

FIGURE 11: ENTREPRENEDU DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE - COVER PAGE

- **PowerPoint template**, created for the purpose of visual aid in terms of presenting project's main objectives, values, strategies, both internally and externally.

FIGURE 12: ENTREPRENEDU POWERPOINT TEMPLATE - COVER PAGE

3.2.2 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

ENTREPRENEDU promotional materials have been developed at M2 and will be upgraded during the projects' lifespan by respecting suggestions made by Consortium Partners. Materials represented below support project's visual identity and communicate ENTREPRENEDU mission, team and objectives:

- **Brochure**, created in A5 size and vertical orientation. Another version will be created by the end of M2 in horizontal orientation.

FIGURE 13: ENTREPRENEDU BROCHURE - COVER AND LAST PAGE

We are enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for European education

Our Mission
We want to create and leave a valuable impact!

The general objective of the project ENTREPRENEDU is creating a highly applicable and scalable Venture Building Program, an educational model for the European entrepreneurial ecosystems that will be validated at the end of the project in 3 different educational entities.

Our Objectives
What are we trying to accomplish?

- Perform need analysis of the needs and evaluate innovative regions in terms of entrepreneurial ecosystem in education and best case scenario
- Enhance the collaboration with developed and less developed innovation ecosystems
- Create an educational program to strengthen business leadership capabilities, as well as entrepreneurship of less and evaluate innovative regions
- Validate the scalability of the ENTREPRENEDU methodology and solutions
- Bring together regional high potential start-ups, profit and business opportunities to give an impulse to improve the entrepreneurial ecosystem in the regions targeted by the project

Our Consortium
The ENTREPRENEDU consortium is composed by a group of 8 business and educational entities, from 6 EU countries: Italy, Germany, Belgium, France, Bulgaria, Ireland, cooperating each other in terms of background knowledge, technical competences, capability of new knowledge creation, business and market experiences, and expertise in education domains where the project interventions can be mostly exploited.

A Benchmarking

Identification of the needs of both education and business ecosystems with focus on citizens, SMEs and Public Administrations, which will allow for:

- build upon well-established policies and consolidated results
- collect materials, examples and best practices that will work as inspiration and suggestions

B Generation of ideas and innovative business solutions

40 teams will participate in a day Hackathons (Online, Soft and AI-based) organized by ENTREPRENEDU's partners and generate ideas and innovative business solutions or strengthen the quality of entrepreneurial education and local talents.

C Mentoring & Coaching

10 teams and startups selected during Hackathons will receive up to 100 hours of mentoring through webinars and coaching workshops in six strategic topics:

- Pitch deck design
- Access to finance and related funding
- Business Model Design
- Education data, services and products
- Acceleration programs and VC pitching
- Investment, cash flow and approach

Qualified teams will support the consortium in the implementation and validation of the venture building program.

D Venture Building Program

Up to 10 students will have the opportunity to pitch a business idea and participate in the Venture Building Program as an incubator for activity via an external call for a specific idea.

- To access to different mentors and supportive dimensions and materials
- To receive up to 1000 hours of mentoring
- To connect with business accelerators and companies

Users from ENTREPRENEDU programme will be able to:

- 1 Define a tailored Business Model and elaborate a business plan at European level, which can be used to apply for pitch and seeking the investment for start-ups.
- 2 Apply to one or more Regional incubators (eg. SBA, Clusters, Networks, etc.) and for European financial support instruments (eg. ITC Pilot, Start Up Europe, Invest Partners, etc.)
- 3 Prepare a pitch presentation and attend investment events, to participate in one of these online and/or private stakeholders.
- 4 Identify and reach in further acceleration programs at regional, national or European level, to coordinate the development and commercialization of the idea.

ENTREPRENEDU community

3 Low and moderate European countries
Italy, Bulgaria and Greece

Start-ups and incubators
regardless of their sector

Educational entities
VET, universities, high schools

Business accelerators and incubation service providers
accelerators, accelerators, science parks, incubators, agencies, consultants, service others

European clusters/networks
eg. ITC, IRI, E-INNOVATORS, ESA-BG, COSE (Greece), among others

Policy makers and decision-making bodies, educational entities
both EU and regional level

FIGURE 14: ENTREPRENEDU BROCHURE - CONTENT

- **Poster**, created in A1 size.

FIGURE 15: ENTREPRENEDU POSTER - COVER PAGE

- **Roll Up**, created in standard size.

FIGURE 16: ENTREPRENEDU ROLL UP - MOCKUP

Note: Provided promotional materials are the draft versions and will be subject to changes in terms of content and visual details.

3.2.3 SOCIAL MEDIA PAGES

The ENTREPRENEDU social media communication has a light and friendly tone of voice to encourage interest and engagement from young audiences, as well as professionals to trigger a discussion with key stakeholders. ENTREPRENEDU is already present in the following social

networks, with an aim to awareness about the project's mission, visibility of the community-building activities and generate traffic to other communication channels, such as website:

- **LinkedIn** - [@ENTREPRENEDU](#)

FIGURE 17: ENTREPRENEDU LINKEDIN PAGE

- **Twitter** - [@ENTREPRENEDU](#)

FIGURE 18: ENTREPRENEDU TWITTER PAGE

- **Facebook** - [@ENTREPRENEDU](#)

FIGURE 19: ENTREPRENEDU FACEBOOK PAGE

- **Instagram** - [@entreprenedu.eu](https://www.instagram.com/entreprenedu.eu)

FIGURE 20: ENTREPRENEDU INSTAGRAM PAGE

- **YouTube** - [@entreprenedu](https://www.youtube.com/@entreprenedu)

FIGURE 21: ENTREPRENEDU YOUTUBE PAGE

On the 10th of March 2023 (M2), the overview of ENTREPRENEDU social media total followers is the following:

TABLE 3: PRESENT SOCIAL MEDIA STATUS

SOCIAL NETWORK	FOLLOWERS
LINKEDIN	41
TWITTER	6
FACEBOOK	8
INSTAGRAM	21
YOUTUBE	2
TOTAL	78

3.2.3.1 CONTENT STRATEGY

ENTREPRENEDU content strategy focuses on four different types of content – post, gif, carousel and video. Each of the previously mentioned types could have one (or more) specific goals:

- **Inform:** General social media publications with an aim to provide up-to-date information about the project.
- **Learn:** Focus on sharing helpful and relevant information content from other accounts related to the project.

- **Engage:** Ask relevant questions and seek to gain responses.
- **Activate:** Sharing content with a clear call to action.

In M1, we developed a monthly content calendar to identify key dates and authentic opportunities to share diversified content following different social media campaigns (elaborated later). The monthly content calendar will be updated periodically, based on the results of social media analytics.

SOCIAL MEDIA Attract interest of industry and connect with stakeholder pages and accounts												
<small>We are happy to introduce you with ENTREPRENEDU's social media calendar. (coming soon) You are welcome to share it with Marketing responsibilities within your respective institution. You can copy the caption and create the post on your SM channels or repost it from ENTREPRENEDU SM channels. If you have any suggestions/questions/doubts or need support, feel free to contact Anja (anja@ifta.com).</small>												
<small>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEU #EUInnovationEcosystems #Innovation #entrepreneurs #entrepreneurship</small>												
<small>Fondazione E. Amaldi Fraunhofer IPK EBAN - European Business Angel Network Corallia Cleantech Bulgaria F&S Innovation Luiss Guido Carli University University of Thessaly</small>												
<small>Fondazione E. Amaldi Fraunhofer IPK EBAN - European Business Angel Network Corallia Cleantech Bulgaria F&S Innovation Luiss Guido Carli Κεντρο για Εμπειρογνηση στην Πανεπιστημιο Θεσσαλιας</small>												
<small>@amaldi_e @Fraunhofer_IPK @F&S_Gov @lth_gr @EBAN_org @cleantechBG</small>												
OBJECTIVES												
February 23												
Post #	Type	Goal	Date	CET (approx)	Channel	Campaign	Caption	Twitter Link	LinkedIn Link	Facebook Link	Instagram Link	Partner Support
1	Post	Inform	7 Feb 23	12 - 15h	All	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	*Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement 101020507. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.	https://twitter.com/EntrepreneurEU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/entrepreneur-eu	https://www.facebook.com/entrepreneur.eu	https://www.instagram.com/entrepreneur_eu	NO
2	Post	Inform	8 Feb 23	9 - 12h	All	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	Hello World! 🌍 We are happy to announce the kick-off of the ENTREPRENEDU project! 🎉 Interested? Stay tuned for more information!	https://twitter.com/EntrepreneurEU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/entrepreneur-eu	https://www.facebook.com/entrepreneur.eu	https://www.instagram.com/entrepreneur_eu	YES
3	Carousel	Inform	10 Feb 23	9 - 12h	All	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	Last week, #ENTREPRENEDU team travelled to Italy to hold its Kick-off meeting in Italian Space Agency @spazioitaliano in the lovely city of Rome. The meeting was successfully organized by the Project Coordinator @FondazioneEAmaldi and assembled diverse innovation stakeholders and educational entities from 6 different European countries - Italy, Bulgaria, Greece, Belgium, Germany and Ireland.	https://twitter.com/EntrepreneurEU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/entrepreneur-eu	https://www.facebook.com/entrepreneur.eu	https://www.instagram.com/entrepreneur_eu	YES
4	Video	Inform	10 Feb 23	10 - 14h	LinkedIn/Twitter/Facebook	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	Take an exclusive behind-the-scenes look of the ENTREPRENEDU's kick-off meeting in Rome! w/ Music Voyage Artists @kloosmusic	https://twitter.com/EntrepreneurEU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/entrepreneur-eu	https://www.facebook.com/entrepreneur.eu	/	NO
5	Link sharing	Inform	13 Feb 23	12h	LinkedIn/Twitter/Facebook	LINK SHARING	Interested in the European Innovation Ecosystems (EIE) Work Programme? 📖 The EIE Work Programme, as part of the "Innovative Europe" aims to create more connected, inclusive and efficient innovation ecosystems that support the scaling of companies and spur innovation to address important challenges. Register to this online event and find out more! 📅 https://link.in.euratlus	https://twitter.com/EntrepreneurEU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/entrepreneur-eu	https://www.facebook.com/entrepreneur.eu	/	NO
6	Post	Inform	14 Feb 23	9-14h	LinkedIn	INFORMATIVE CAMPAIGN	Do you have any ideas about what is ENTREPRENEDU and what are we trying to accomplish? 🤔 w/ Read our first press release and let us know if you have any questions in the comments below!	/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/entrepreneur-eu	/	/	YES

FIGURE 22: ENTREPRENEDU PARTNERS DASHBOARD - SOCIAL MEDIA

When formatting the content for publishing on social media, the length of the content is variable, as it depends on the social network and the goal we are trying to accomplish. All posts should ideally be accompanied by an image or a video. The following guidelines will allow content to be brief enough to be quick to read and to grab our audiences' attention, but long enough to offer some details.

TABLE 4: CONTENT PUBLISHING GUIDELINES

SOCIAL NETWORK	CHARACTERS	POSTING FREQUENCY
LINKEDIN / FACEBOOK	~200	Minimum 2 times per week
TWITTER / INSTAGRAM	~100	Minimum 2 times per week

Note: Due to the agility of the project, as well as social media trends, the guidelines above might be subject to changes.

3.2.3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

To increase awareness, drive traffic and engage with stakeholders, as a part of ENTREPRENEDU communication plan, different campaigns were already planned and ready to be implemented in the first six months of the project, while others are to be deployed henceforward, depending on the up-to-date status of the project.

TABLE 5: EXAMPLES OF SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

CAMPAIGN	EXAMPLE OF A KEY MESSAGE	GOAL
KICK-OFF	<p>Last week, #ENTREPRENEDU team travelled to Italy to hold its Kick-off meeting in Italian Space Agency @AgenziaSpazialeItaliana nearby beautiful Rome.</p> <p>The meeting was successfully organised by the Project Coordinator @Fondazione E. Amaldi and assembled diverse innovation stakeholders and educational entities from 6 different European countries - Italy, Bulgaria, Greece, Belgium, Germany and Ireland.</p>	INFORM

<p>INFORMATIVE</p>	<p>You are looking at our social media pages, but you are interested in learning more? 🤔</p> <p>Well... We are here to help!</p> <p>You can always 📩 us at hello@entreprenedu.eu for any of your thoughts about #ENTREPRENEDU project 🙌</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>INFORM</p>
<p>AWARENESS</p>	<p>ENTREPRENEDU stands for enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education. 📖</p> <p>Our objective is to support, share knowledge, build confidence, provide advices, as well as best practices to future #entrepreneurs! 🙌</p> <p>We offer a business #opportunity for high school and university students to build their professional path more easily and potentially create new EU based #unicorn companies!</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>INFORM ENGAGE</p>
<p>ECOSYSTEM NEWS</p>	<p>Interested in the European Innovation Ecosystems (EIE) Work Programme? 🙌</p> <p>The EIE Work Programme, as part of the “Innovative Europe” aims to create more connected, inclusive and efficient #innovation ecosystems that support the scaling of companies and spur innovation to address important challenges.</p> <p>Register to this online event and find out more 📩</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/eRAtTxAj</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>LEARN ACTION</p>

<p>WEBSITE</p>	<p>What better way to start this Monday than announcing that ENTREPRENEDU website is no longer under maintenance? 🙌</p> <p>It looks young & modern as our main target audience and it's ready to enhance entrepreneurial ecosystems for education in a big style!</p> <p>Take a quick look and let us know what you think in the comments 🙌</p> <p>www.entreprenedu.eu</p> <p>P.S. What is your #HappyMonday news?</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>ACTION ENGAGE</p>
<p>MEET THE TEAM</p>	<p>Today we are travelling directly to Rome, Italy to meet @Fondazione E. Amaldi! 🙌</p> <p>E. Amaldi Foundation (FEA) is an Italian organisation for applied research, technology transfer and the promotion and support of the national scientific heritage and ENTREPRENEDU's Project Coordinator. Born in 2017, they believe in open innovation and that is why they act as accelerators for all the players that operate in the field of technology transfer or who are interested in shortening the time in terms of innovation acquisition.</p> <p>Interested in space missions? Learn more about them! 🙌</p> <p>www.entreprenedu.eu</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>ENGAGE INFORM</p>

<p>NEWSLETTER</p>	<p>Are you thinking about becoming an entrepreneur, but you are not sure where to start?</p> <p>We will enhance your email inbox with the “fresh from oven” information about business, leadership, education and of course - entrepreneurship! 🙌</p> <p>You know you have 5 seconds – subscribe to the world of entrepreneurship now! 🙌</p> <p>WWW.ENTREPRENEDU.EU</p>	<p>ENGAGE</p> <p>ACTION</p>
<p>HACKATHONS</p>	<p>#ENTREPRENEDU project is an adventure filled with possibilities, important missions and interesting events for future entrepreneurs 🚀 One of those events are 3 ENTREPRENEDU Hackathons that will be organised in Italy, Bulgaria and Greece!</p> <p>We are already preparing the #ENTREPRENEDU Hackathon #1 🙌 Any ideas about the theme?</p>	<p>INFORM</p> <p>ENGAGE</p>

3.2.3.3 SOCIAL MEDIA TEMPLATES

ENTREPRENEDU social media templates have been developed at M1 and will be upgraded during the projects’ lifespan by respecting suggestions made by Consortium Partners. As a part of the project’s branding, the set of social media templates has a goal to strengthen ENTREPRENEDU’s online communication and dissemination strategy, as well as to establish an effective online presence on project’s official social media channels.

Figure 23: ENTREPRENEDU SOCIAL MEDIA TEMPLATE – VERSION A

FIGURE 24: ENTREPRENEDU SOCIAL MEDIA TEMPLATE – VERSION B

FIGURE 25: ENTREPRENEU SOCIAL MEDIA TEMPLATE - VERSION C

FIGURE 26: ENTREPRENEU SOCIAL MEDIA TEMPLATE - VERSION D

3.2.4 WEBSITE

The ENTREPRENEDU website (www.entreprenedu.eu) was developed in M2 and envisioned as visually oriented and interactive, with an engaging tone of voice. It follows the official brand identity and targets ENTREPRENEDU key stakeholders.

The website incorporates the basic information that elaborates key concepts of the project and calls to action through the following sections:

- The **Home page** represents an overview of the project, main objectives, an overview of all respective partners involved in the project and a call to action to the project's newsletter.
- The **Journey page** showcased different phases of ENTREPRENEDU's journey from the perspective of the main stakeholders.
- The **Insight page** includes three subpages (Blog, Press Kit, Communication Kit) which together represent an overview of the communication aspects, such as communication materials, attended events, press area that supplement the journalist story and similar.
- The **Contact page** represents the possibility for all interested parties to contact us and leave any comment they feel is relevant.

Note: Due to the agility of the project, the sections above might be subject to changes, as F6S will be preparing the second iteration of the ENTREPRENEDU website.

The content of the website will be displayed using the different social media channels of the project. The ENTREPRENEDU website statistics will be regularly monitored by the Communication Manager.

On the left side of the website there is a blue icon which refers to Accessibility Tools with an aim of enhancing users' experience on ENTREPRENEDU website.

FIGURE 27: ACCESSIBILITY TOOL AT THE ENTREPRENEDU WEBSITE

FIGURE 28: ENTREPRENEU WEBSITE - HOMEPAGE

3.2.5 F6S PLATFORM

F6S (www.f6s.com) is the largest and fastest growing social platform for founders, startups and small and medium enterprises (SMEs). With over 4,5 million users and over 200.000

startups/SME F6S has become the #1 startup/SME community globally. Additionally, through the F6S Platform, ENTREPRENEDU will be able to reach 250.000 users and 30.000 startups/SMEs in Europe and more than 7.000 investors.

With these numbers in mind, we have used F6S Platform to create an ENTREPRENEDU Accelerator page in M1, which will be further exploited during the lifetime of the project for promoting special social media campaigns focused on ENTREPRENEDU Hackathons, all with an aim of building awareness around these events and rising the ENTREPRENEDU community. This way, information posted in the ENTREPRENEDU Accelerator page will be automatically placed to the larger community, leveraging its outreach, and bringing closer attention to the project.

FIGURE 29: ENTREPRENEDU PAGE AT F6S PLATFORM

3.2.6 NEWSLETTER

A minimum of 4 project newsletters per year will be developed using Mailchimp and circulated via email lists providing an overview of the main project activities and outcomes. The first newsletter will be sent in the M3 of the project with an aim to increase the project's awareness and promote the ENTREPRENEDU website. On every page of the website, interested parties will have a possibility to subscribe to the ENTREPRENEDU newsletter and get the latest insights of the project, as well as up-to-date trends from the European innovation ecosystem.

The structure of the newsletter will be developed according to the project's up-to-date activities, and it may contain the following information:

- Newsletter banner,
- Newsletter title,
- Project highlights,
- Project updates,
- Event promotion,
- Partners updates,
- News from the ecosystem,
- Diverse social media calls to actions.

Note: Due to the agility of the project, the list above might be subject to changes.

All Consortium Partners will be asked regularly to contribute to the newsletter with image and text content regarding their Work Package activities. Moreover, to boost the impact of the ENTREPRENEDU newsletter strategy, we will create a Newsletter blurb – a summarised newsletter to be shared across Partners’ newsletter.

3.2.7 BLOG ARTICLES

A minimum of 3 blog publications targeting relevant stakeholders will be written to create awareness and communicate about ENTREPRENEDU's activities.

So far, we have developed a blog post titled “ENTREPRENEDU project kicks off in Rome”, which is already available at ENTREPRENEDU’s website.

FIGURE 30: FIRST ENTREPRENEDU BLOG POST

3.2.8 PROMOTIONAL VIDEOS

A set of minimum 3 multimedia video podcasts presenting the project, its innovation and key outcomes will be developed during the lifetime of the project targeting specific and/or all stakeholders. Additionally, the video materials will be uploaded to the ENTREPRENEDU's official YouTube channel and the website.

The following promotional materials is planned to be created:

- "A word from a Project Coordinator" video will be created at the beginning of the project in collaboration with Eleonora Lombardi, ENTREPRENEDU's Project Coordinator in a structure of an interview.
- An **explanatory video** will showcase the general information about the project, its mission and objectives.
- **Results video** will display the key project results and the impact ENTREPRENEDU has established during its life cycle.

Note: Due to the agility of the project, the list above might be subject to changes.

3.2.9 ADDITIONAL COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

With an aim of elevating the ENTREPRENEDU internal and external communication strategy, additional communication activities have been undertaken, while others are already foreseen:

- **Brand Guidelines** is a general template following the ENTREPRENEDU brand identity with a goal to unify communication activities, both internally and externally.
- **Newsletter blurb** is a cross-linking banner with a textual message which will be prepared in M3, together with an official newsletter, with an aim to increase projects' initial awareness.
- **Blog guidelines** is a document which aims to ease the participation of Consortium Partners in communication activities, by describing in detail how to write the blog article.

4 DISSEMINATION PLAN

An effective dissemination strategy was developed to facilitate wide-spread information transfer among and beyond the Consortium members, increase public awareness as well as external visibility. Therefore, ENTREPRENEDU's dissemination methodology will be focused on a unique strategy for disseminating the results of the project targeting the European Innovation ecosystems. With direct contribution by all Consortium Partners, the strategy will

TABLE 6: LIST OF POTENTIAL MEDIA PUBLICATIONS

NUMBER	TENTATIVE MONTH	TENTATIVE TOPIC
1	M1	<u>ENTREPRENEDU – Enhancing Entrepreneurial Ecosystems for Education</u>
2	M6	Hackathon #1
3	M12	Hackathon #2
4	M18	Hackathon #3

Note: Due to the agility of the project, the table above represents a preliminary calendar of content that will be updated in the future according to the project's up-to-date activities and achieved milestones.

So far, one press release has been created, titled “ENTREPRENEDU – Enhancing Entrepreneurial Ecosystems for Education” and [available for download](#) at ENTREPRENEDU website.

FIGURE 33: FIRST ENTREPRENEDU PRESS RELEASE

4.2.2 SCIENTIFIC PAPERS

In academic publishing, ENTREPRENEDU project targets the publication of a minimum of 6 scientific articles and/or abstracts submitted to relevant conferences, which will be produced as a joint effort between Consortium Partners. Currently ENTREPRENEDU has submitted an abstract for the technical session of the [International Astronautical Congress 2023](#) subject to approval by the scientific committee of the event (envisaged deadline for feedback is 25th April 2023).

74th International Astronautical Congress 2023

 Paper ID: 79044
 oral

 IAF BUSINESSES AND INNOVATION SYMPOSIUM (E6)
 Entrepreneurship Around the World (5-GTS.1)

 Author: Dr. Valerio Roscani
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 ENHANCING THE EUROPEAN ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEM BY CLOSING THE GAP
 BETWEEN HIGH AND LOW/MODERATE INNOVATION REGIONS: THE ENTREPRENEDU CASE

Abstract

The European entrepreneurial ecosystems are facing increasing global competition, nevertheless closing the innovation gap among European countries and regions is still a necessity to provide education schemes and supporting mechanisms for youth and startups. Technologically driven sectors such as spacetechnology and deeptech are well suited for innovation but new entrepreneurs, students and researchers often lack the necessary know-how to build a resilient and successful business. To provide the right expertise, support the birth of innovative ideas and ultimately strengthen entrepreneurial ecosystems the project ENTREPRENEDU - Enhancing Entrepreneurial Ecosystems for Education - brings together several innovation stakeholders and educational entities from 6 different European countries, 3 low/moderate innovative regions Italy, Bulgaria and Greece and 3 high innovative regions Belgium, Germany and Ireland. ENTREPRENEDU - is a Horizon Europe financed programme, coordinated by Fondazione E. Amaldi, that aims to create a more innovative, entrepreneurial and sustainable European higher education system. The project is conceived for students, young entrepreneurs and start-ups working in the space economy, deep tech and green and digital transition and aims at creating a high replicable and scalable Venture Building Program for both businesses and educational systems via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level, supporting developed concept and ideas to become concrete solutions. ENTREPRENEDU aims to foster the birth of innovative ideas that will have an impact on both the Green Deal and the SDGs, as well as on gender equality with the goal of having concrete projects for a better and more sustainable world. The goal of this paper is to illustrate the best practices regarding the structuring and implementation of the scalable and replicable ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building programme. This study will present the results of the context and stakeholder analysis, as well as the results of the first hackathon focusing on the space economy, the feedback, and the needs of the participating teams and start-ups.

FIGURE 34: ENTREPRENEDU SCIENTIFIC PAPER ABSTRACT - UNDER EVALUATION

4.2.3 PARTICIPATION IN NETWORKING EVENTS

Dissemination events will be important as they act as places to establish presence, build liaisons, and engage key stakeholders in the social media ecosystem. Therefore, we have prepared an internal event management document in M2 that will be shared with all partners. The objective of this document is to gather information concerning events of interest with details such as dates, contact info about the organiser and whether a partner will attend. This dashboard will be a 'live' tool, regularly updated depending on the present project status.

EVENTS Liaison with stakeholders of the community															
ATTENDED															
Partner name	Event Name	Start Date	End Date	Status	Event Type	Information Link	Audience Type	City	Country	Goal/Impact	Photos	Learnings	Fee	Comments	
PROPOSED															
Event Name	Start Date	End Date	Event Type	Information Link	Audience Type	City	Country	Reasoning	Fee	Comments					

FIGURE 35: ENTREPRENEDU PARTNERS DASHBOARD – EVENTS

Moreover, as a part of the dissemination strategy, the attended events reported in this table will be announced on the project website, social media platforms, and on the project newsletter.

4.2.4 SYNERGIES WITH HORIZON PROJECTS

With an aim to enhance ENTREPRENEDU’s impact, we will find synergies with other relevant projects under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. So far, we have identified 3 potential synergies between ENTREPRENEDU and:

- [SPREAD2INNO](#) has an aim of spreading the global potential of developing innovation ecosystems to strengthen innovation in regional and local businesses.
- [AccelerAction](#) has an aim of connecting DeepTech innovators across Europe.
- [SYNBEE](#) has an aim of expanding synthetic biology entrepreneurial ecosystems.

4.2.5 DISSEMINATION OF PUBLIC DELIVERABLES

The public deliverables will be uploaded on the ENTREPRENEDU website representing an opportunity to share early results and external dissemination. On the other hand, the private deliverables will only be summarised.

The public deliverables are listed below:

- **D1.3** - Quality Assurance Plan;
- **D1.6** - Quality Assurance Plan - final release;
- **D2.1** - Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario;
- **D2.2** - Public guideline on specific needs for low moderate innovation regions;
- **D3.1** - Hackathon Handbook Template;

- **D3.2** - Hackathons implementation report;
- **D4.1** - Mentoring modules;
- **D4.2** - Report on mentoring activities;
- **D4.4** - Mentoring modules - final release;
- **D4.5** - Report on mentoring activities - final release;
- **D4.6** - Feedback collection - final release;
- **D5.1** - Call for students;
- **D5.2** - Syllabus of the Venture Building course;
- **D5.4** - Fine-tuning survey on the venture building program and related Fellowship;
- **D6.2** - Publication of 3 guidelines on the ENTREPRENEDU standard operating procedures;
- **D6.3** - 3 MoU signed with other EU initiatives and/or educational entities;
- **D7.1** - Dissemination and communication plan;
- **D7.2** - Dissemination and communication plan - final release.

4.2.6 ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION ACTIONS

With an aim of elevating the ENTREPRENEDU's dissemination strategy, additional dissemination supportive materials have been undertaken, while others are already foreseen:

- **Event Guidelines** is a document elaborating the step-by-step guidelines and event management tips with an aim to create an easy-to-implement system to promote and disseminate participation in both hosted and events to be attended.
- **Press Kit** is a document showcasing the key points of the ENTREPRENEDU project with an aim to drive traffic and engage with the media.
- **Standard Project Presentation** is a presentation that elaborates project's methodology and objectives. This document is developed for external usage with an aim to engage with key stakeholders.

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MONITORING PLAN

The management and monitoring of the dissemination and communication plan is led by F6S, Work Package 7 – Communication and dissemination leader, although all partners are participating in the implementation activities as contribution from all respective partners is always welcomed and appreciated. Moreover, all partners are aware of the activities proposed and regularly updated about the achieved results.

5.1 ACTION PLAN

The ENTREPRENEDU action plan is outlined according to the timeline of key communication and dissemination activities and results to be communicated. Moreover, the timeline includes the information related to public deliverables and milestones which are relevant to communicate along the project lifespan.

FIGURE 36: ENTREPRENEDU ACTION PLAN - GANTT CHART

Moreover, we have prepared several main points of the ENTREPRENEDU action plan in order to enhance its effectiveness:

- The communication and dissemination activities are led by F6S, with a contribution from all respective Consortium Partners.
- Consortium Partners have the responsibility of contributing to the creation of content related to their Work Package activities and distributing them in their respective communication and dissemination channels.
- All Consortium Partners play a crucial role in communicating and disseminating ENTREPRENEDU related activities at a local, national, and European level. Thus, it is important that they are aware of the timeline of key results to be communicated, as well as of the set of communication tools made available in the official shared cloud.
- All Consortium Partners are welcome to contribute to the Partners Dashboard – an internal means of communication including all relevant communication and dissemination activities (media base, stakeholders base, newsletter schedule, social media schedule...).
- At any point, all Consortium Partners are welcome to contact F6S in case of any questions or concerns related to Work Package 7 – Communication and dissemination.

5.2 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

By referring to the Grant Agreement, in the table below, we have represented the communication, exploitation and dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

TABLE 7: ENTREPRENEDEDU KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

CHANNELS	OBJECTIVE	RELATED KPI	THRESHOLD
WEBSITE	Interest generated towards the value chain and other stakeholders (including the public at large)	# of visits # of hits per page # of references of the website on other sites	Website in M2 >1000 unique visitors >20 references in other websites
SOCIAL MEDIA	Interacting with the general public through Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube	# of followers # of tweets # of views per promoted post	>200 followers on each social media page >80 tweets >500 views per post
VIDEOS	Awareness	# of videos	3 promotional videos
JOURNAL/MAGAZINE ARTICLES, NEWSLETTERS, PRESS RELEASES	Publication intensity	# of published articles # of magazine news frequency of newsletter # of scientific paper released	>6 journal articles >3 magazines news >4 newsletters per year >6 scientific papers released
INTERNATIONAL/NATIONAL CONFERENCES, SEMINARS, WORKSHOPS AND MEETINGS WITH CLUSTERS AND ASSOCIATIONS	Enlarge the interest in other sectors/areas, transferring knowledge, lessons learned and results	# of project outreach sessions # of presentations # of participants per event # of social media campaigns	>4 project outreach events >4 total project presentations >50 participants 3 social media campaigns
EVENTS IN THE REFERENCE SECTOR FOCUSING ON BOTH PROFESSIONAL AND GENERAL PUBLIC	Enlarge the interest within sectors/areas, transferring knowledge, lessons learned and results	# of events # of overall business negotiations # of overall commercial agreements	>4 events >3 MoU signed >3 signed collaboration partnerships
CLUSTERING WITH OTHER NATIONAL AND EU INITIATIVES	Connect with different networks, experts to share experiences, knowledge and best practices	# of national and EU initiatives contacted	2-3 connections created

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS	Link with policy makers enabling a real adoption of project's results	# of supporting letters # of policy recommendations # of best practice manuals	>8 supporting letters >2 recommendations >1 best practice inventory >3 guidelines on standard operating procedures
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To measure the key indicators above, the following evaluation elements will be used:

- **Google Analytics** to track and report the project website traffic.
- **Social Media metrics** to track the engagement on ENTREPRENEDU's social networks.
- **Partners Dashboard** as an internal "live" document to track all previously mentioned communication and dissemination activities, with contribution of all Consortium Partners included.

5.3 IMPACT EVALUATION

After adapting the written material in the first version of the ENTREPRENEDU's Dissemination and Communication Plan, we could expect the following impacts of the project:

- **Scientific:** New discovery on barriers solutions for business knowledge in education for youth and startups, by reinforcing best practices and publication of 3 new guidelines.
- **Economic:** Youth and startups overcoming existing barriers and becoming able to develop proposed concepts, while getting closer to the business market.
- **Societal:** Stronger regional connections which enable scaling of needs and increasing exchange of information and talent across Europe, while unlocking potential of regions that have not yet fully developed their innovation ecosystems.

6 FINAL REMARKS

This document outlines the first release plan for communication and dissemination activities, with an aim to structure and coordinate activities and efforts to ensure the intended outcomes and specific objectives of the project were met. The dissemination and communication strategy of the ENTREPRENEDU project aims at maximising its impact by connecting the support activities performed to the public and professional audiences. Hence, in order to guarantee an overall coherent and unique voice for the project, the envisaged strategy developed by F6S was tailored to contribute to the achieving of the overall project goal, reaching the defined target groups and making sure that the key messages of the project were disseminated. The implementation of the dissemination and communication consists of the integration of all networking activities by Consortium Partners and collaborators in order to maximise the effect and reach the widest, and most relevant, audience possible such as actors and facilitators, but also far beyond than the primarily targeted innovation ecosystems.

In order to achieve this, ENTREPRENEDU communication team has developed an effective strategic approach, as well as materials and tools to be used by all consortium partners across project activities, while the planned activities and results will be disseminated throughout the lifespan of the project. Moreover, strategies to ensure sustainable scalability of the project final outcomes have also been considered while developing this plan. Of course, as a living document responding to new development and opportunities, updates of the communication and dissemination planned activities can be made upon approval by the Consortium Partners during the implementation process of the project and will be monitored through an internal reporting procedure involving all ENTREPRENEDU partners (M6, M12, M18, M24) which will ensure that the goals and targets set are being achieved, identify any potential issues and hence correct or amend tasks and where applicable.

In this context, **Deliverable 7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN** is meant to be used as a strategic springboard for the Deliverable **D7.2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN – FINAL RELEASE** which will represent a more comprehensive plan and another evaluation method of the Deliverable 7.1.